

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Title (clearly states "Systematic Review and Meta-analysis")
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Abstract (includes background, goals, methods, results, and conclusions)
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Introductory text (explains global burden of ACCE and gaps in self-management research)
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	End of introduction (lists 4 goals)
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Methods section (PICOS criteria; studies grouped by stroke, myocardial infarction, sudden cardiac death)
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Search strategy description (7 databases: Cochrane, PubMed, etc.; last searched 6 March 2025)
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Search strategy (Supplementary Table 1)
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Study selection section (2 reviewers screened independently; 3rd resolved disagreements)
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Data extraction section (2 reviewers extracted data independently; 4th resolved disagreements)
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Inclusion criteria (focus on self-efficacy, functional independence, quality of life)
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Data extraction details (e.g. study design, sample size, theoretical basis; summarized in Table 1)
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Quality assessment section (used Cochrane Risk of Bias tool; 2 reviewers assessed independently)
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Statistical methods (used standardized mean difference [SMD] with 95% CI)
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Synthesis methods (studies grouped by ACCE subtype for analysis)
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Statistical methods (imputed missing SDs using Cochrane guidelines)
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Results section (uses forest plots in Figs. 3a–3e)

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Statistical methods (used random-effects/fixed-effects models based on I ² ; RevMan 5.4.1 software)
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Synthesis methods (subgroup analyses by ACCE subtype)
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Not conducted (stated in limitations)
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Publication bias section (used funnel plots for stroke self-efficacy)
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Not conducted (stated in limitations)
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Search results (PRISMA flow diagram in Fig. 1; 2081 records → 30 studies included)
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Search results (22 excluded studies; reasons: non-RCT, no target outcomes)
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Study characteristics section (Table 1 lists 30 studies with details like country, sample size, theory)
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Risk of bias section (Fig. 2 summarizes: 40% low risk, 46.7% some concerns, 13.3% high risk)
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Synthesis results (forest plots in Figs. 3a–3e include group means, SDs, and effect sizes)
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Synthesis results (describes study features and bias for each ACCE subtype)
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Synthesis results (e.g., stroke self-efficacy: SMD=0.49, 95% CI[0.19,0.78], I ² =85%)
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Synthesis results (reports I ² values and interpretation)
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Not applicable (no sensitivity analyses)
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Publication bias section (funnel plot showed asymmetry for stroke self-efficacy)
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Not applicable (no certainty assessment)
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Discussion (links findings to prior reviews on stroke self-management)
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Discussion (notes short intervention durations, measurement variability)

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Limitations section (highlights heterogeneity, variable theory application depth)
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Discussion and Conclusion (calls for better theory-technique alignment in future studies)
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Abstract and methods (PROSPERO: CRD420251005366)
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Methods (protocol accessible via PROSPERO)
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	No amendments (stated in methods)
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Funding statement (lists Yunnan projects; funders had no role in the study)
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Conflict of interest statement (no conflicts declared)
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Data availability statement (data from included studies; raw data available from original authors)

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. This work is licensed under CC BY 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>